

GLOBAL JOURNAL OF ENGINEERING SCIENCE AND RESEARCHES
APPLICATION OF PROBABILITY IN QUEUING THEORY

Madhu. S. Palod¹, Damodhar F Shastrakar² & Bhalchandra H Ganthade³

^{1,2&3}Department of Mathematics, Smt Radhikatai Pandav College of Engineering, Nagpur

ABSTRACT

This paper be discovered about the history of queuing theory. Its origin and its application in our day to day problems also use of probability distribution in queuing theory. Initial inventions of queuing theory and its applications were discussed in this paper

Keywords: Probability; queuing; theory arrival time, servicetime telephone, manual swiutchboard.

I. INTRODUCTION

Humans have practiced gambling at all times. The archaeologists have made excavations in prehistoric sites and found large numbers of roughly dice-shaped bones. Different sorts of recreations, sports volleyball, occasions, and betting are associated on the grounds that it has dependably been difficult to make wagers on various results of a diversion.

Fig2: Playing with dice relief from ancient Rome

Encounters and straightforward insights utilized pretty much unknowingly made in old circumstances the reason for the card sharks and their wagering. Until the sixteenth century the arithmetic was not connected on betting and likelihood issues.

This paper demonstrates how betting issues started the numerical hypothesis of likelihood and gives a review of the foundation of the scientific hypothesis of likelihood. The lines are drawn from the scientific hypothesis of likelihood to the foundation of the lining/teletraffic hypothesis over 200 years after the fact. Furthermore, the pioneers in building up the lining/teletraffic hypothesis were Agner Krarup Erlang and Tore Olaus Engset! (Stordahl, 2006) recognized that The Gambler's Ruin Problem was understood by utilizing an indistinguishable distinction conditions from for the M/M/1 lining frameworks, just 200 years sooner. This paper researches and clarifies the instigations for the improvement of the lining/teletraffic hypothesis which was for the most part caused by presentation of phone exchanging frameworks.

Fig2: Gambling, caricature of an early roulette table, ca 1800

The telephone and the manual switches

1. Telephoneswitches

Following the innovation of the phone in 1876, the main phones were leased in sets which were constrained to discussion between the gatherings working those two instruments. The utilization of a focal trade was soon observed to be considerably more beneficial than in telecommunication. In January 1878 the Boston Telephone Dispatch organization had begun contracting young men as phone administrators. Young men had been exceptionally fruitful as telecommunication administrators, yet their mentality, absence of tolerance, and conduct was unsuitable for live phone contact,[1] so the organization started procuring ladies administrators. Along these lines, on September 1, 1878, Boston Telephone Dispatch contracted Emma Nutt as the principal lady administrator. Residential communities regularly had the switchboard introduced in the administrator's home with the goal that he or she could answer approaches a 24-hour premise. In 1894, New England Telephone and Telegraph Company introduced the principal battery-worked switchboard on January 9 in Lexington, Massachusetts1. (Alexander graham bell (1847-1922) the later inventor of the telephone

II. MANUAL SWITCHBOARD

Prior to the coming of Automatic Switching, all Telephone Connections were made by hand at the Manual Switchboard, Figure 1. The Calling Customer rang up an Operator, at a Switching Office, which, in the wake of knowing the quantity of the Called Customer, interconnected the relating Lines, to Close the Circuit, with a specific end goal to finish the Call.

Fig. 3: Manual Switchboard

Operating switchboard by Air force Officer
Fig.4: U.S. Air Force operator works a switchboard

The switchboard is generally intended to suit the administrator, who sits confronting it. It has a high back board, which comprises of lines of female jacks, each jack assigned and wired as a neighborhood expansion of the switchboard (which serves an individual supporter) or as an approaching or friendly trunk line. The jack is additionally connected with a light.

On the table or work area zone before the administrator are sections of keys, lights and lines. Every segment comprises of a front key and a back key, a front light and a back light, trailed by a front rope and a back rope, making up together a rope circuit. The front key is the "talk" key enabling the administrator to talk with that specific rope match. The back key on more seasoned "manual" sheets and PBXs is accustomed to ring a phone physically. On more current sheets, the back key is utilized to gather (recover) cash from coin phones. Each of the keys has three positions: back, typical and forward. At the point when a key is in the typical position an electrical talk way interfaces the front and back strings. A key in the forward position (front key) interfaces the administrator to the string pair, and a key in the back position sends a ring signal out on the string (on more established manual trades). Each line has a three-wire TRS telephone connector: tip and ring for testing, ringing and voice; and a sleeve wire for occupied signs.

Probability

Likelihood is the probability that an occasion will happen and is ascertained by separating the quantity of positive results by the aggregate number of conceivable results. The least difficult case is a coin flip. When you flip a coin

there are just two conceivable results, the outcome is either heads or tails. Thus the likelihood of getting takes is 1 off of 2, or $\frac{1}{2}$, or half. The table beneath demonstrates the dispersion of the likelihood of every result. There is a half possibility the result will be heads, and there is a half shot the result will be tails.

Likelihood dispersion is a numerical capacity that, expressed in basic terms, can be thought of as giving the probabilities of event of various conceivable results in an investigation. For example, if the irregular variable X is utilized to indicate the result of a coin hurl ("the analysis"), at that point the likelihood conveyance of X would take the esteem 0.5 for X = heads, and 0.5 for X = tails (expecting the coin is reasonable).

Likelihood conveyances are by and large separated into two classes.

- 1) A discrete likelihood conveyance (material to the situations where the arrangement of conceivable results is discrete, for example, a coin hurl or a move of dice) can be encoded by a discrete rundown of the probabilities of the results, known as a likelihood mass capacity.
- 2) A persistent likelihood dissemination (appropriate to the situations where the arrangement of conceivable results can go up against values in a constant range (e.g. genuine numbers, for example, the temperature on a given day) is normally portrayed by likelihood thickness capacities (with the likelihood of any individual result really being

There are a wide range of kinds of likelihood appropriations in measurements including:

- Basic likelihood disseminations which can be appeared on a likelihood conveyance table.
- Binomial disseminations, which have "Triumphs" and "Disappointments."

Ordinary dispersions, some of the time called a Bell Curve).

Exampall: Three coins are being tossed; find the probability distribution of getting any number of tails.

Solution:

Sample space, S = {HHH, HHT, HTH, THH, HTT, THT, TTH, TTT}

Hence, in tossing three coins number of tails can be 0, 1, 2, 3.

Probability of getting 0 tails, $P(X=0) = 1/8$

Probability of getting 1 tails, $P(X=1) = 3/8$

Probability of getting 2 tails, $P(X=2) = 3/8$

Probability of getting 3 tails, $P(X=3) = 1/8$

Probability distribution can be given as:

X	0	1	2	3
P(X)	1/8	3/8	3/8	1/8

Queuing theory and Queuing models

Queuing hypothesis is the numerical investigation of holding up lines, or lines. The hypothesis empowers numerical investigation of a few related processes, including touching base at the queue, waiting in the line and being served by the server at the front of the line.

- The least complex type of lining models depend on the birth and process, where the birth procedure portrays the between entry time to the line and the passing procedure depicts the administration or holding time in the line.
- For queuing hypothesis, it has been discovered convenient, if conceivable, to work with likelihood circulation which display the memory lessness property, as this regularly improves the arithmetic included

III. CONCLUSION

By using queuing theory the problems of forming queue faced by the human being can be resolved to some extent. This theory is beneficial for human being to increase the satisfaction level and decrease the waiting time in the queue.

REFERENCES

1. Anish Amin, Piyush Mehta , Abhilekh Sahay, Pranesh Kumar And Arun Kumar (2014),“Optimal Solution of Real Time Problems Using Queuing Theory”, International Journal of Engineering and Innovative Technology, Vol. 3 Issue 10, pp.268-270.
2. Babes M, Serma GV (1991), “Out-patient Queues at the Ibn-Rochd Health Centre”, Journal of the Operations Research 42(10), pp.1086-1087. [4]Bose K. Sanjay (2002), “An Introduction to Queuing System”, Springer US
3. Dhari K, Tanzina Rahman (2013), “Case Study For Bank ATM Queuing Models”, IOSR Journal of Mathematics, pp.01-05.
4. Hana Sedlakova (2012), “Priority Queuing Systems M/G/I”, Thesis, University of West Bohemia.
5. Janos Sztrik (2010), “Queuing Theory and Its Application”, A Personal View, 8th International Conference on Applied Infomatics, Vol. 1, pp.9-30.
6. Kantiswarup, Gupta P.K., Manmohan (2012), “Operations Research”, Excel Books Private Ltd. New Delhi, pp.215- 231.
7. Manuel Alberto M.Ferreira, Marina Andrade , Jose Antonio Fillpe and Manuel Pacheco Coelho (2011), “Statistical Queuing Theory With Some Applications”, International Journal Latest trends Fin.Eco.Sc.pp.190-195.
8. Mital K.M. (2010), “Queuing Analysis For Out Patient and Inpatient Services: A Case Study” ,Management Decision, Vol. 48, No. 3 , pp.419-439.
9. Muhammad Imran Qureshi, Mansoor Bhatti, Aamir Khan and Khalid Zaman (2014), “Measuring Queuing System and Time Standards: A Case Study of Student Affairs In Universities”, African Journal of Business Management Vol.8(2),pp.80-88.
10. Muhammad Marsudi, Hani Shafeek (2014), “The Application of Queuing Theory In Multi-stage Production”, Line ,International Conference on Industrial Engineering and Operations Management Bali, Indonesia, pp.668-673.
11. Patel B.,Bhathawala P.(2012), “Case Study for Bank ATM Queuing Model”, International Journal of Engineering Research and Application, Vol.2, pp.1278-1284.
12. Pieter-Tjerk de Boer’s (2000), “Analysis And Efficient Simulation of Queuing Models of Telecommunication Systems”, ISBN 90-365-1505-X, ISSN 1381-3617, CTIT Ph.D.-Thesis Series No. 00-01.
13. Pokley S.S.,Gakhare S.S.(2002), “Waiting Line Theory Applied To Adequate Requirement Of Beds In Hospital”, “Business Perspectives”,Birla Inst.of Management Technology, Vol 4,No.2,pp.77-80.
14. Shastrakar D. F., Pokley S.S., Patil K.D. (2016), “Literature Review of Waiting Lines Theory and its Applications in Queuing Model”,International Journal of Engineering Research and Technology, Special Issue-2016, IC-QUEST-2016 Conference Proceeding, pp.13-15.
15. Shastrakar D. F., Pokley S.S.,(2017), “Study of Different Parameters for the Electricity Bills Cash Counter Queuing Model”,International Journal of Innovations in Engineering and Science, Vol.2 N0. 6, e-ISSN: 2456-3463, pp.195-197
16. Shastrakar D. F., Pokley S.S.,(2017),“Analysis of Different Parameters of Queuing Theory for the Waiting Time of Patients in Hospital”,International Conference On Emanations in Modern Engineering Science and Management, Vol.5, Issue:3,ISSN: 2321-8169, pp. 98-100.

[ICEMESM-18]

DOI-10.5281/zenodo.1226625

ISSN 2348 - 8034

Impact Factor- 5.070

17. Shastrakar D. F., Pokley S.S., (2017), "Application of Queuing Theory to Minimize the Waiting Time of Customer at Bill Paying Counter of Supermarket", International Journal for Research in Applied Science & Engineering Technology, Vol.5, Issue:IX, ISSN: 2321-9653, pp. 8-10.